

Studies on Ferrocene and Its Derivatives. IV. Some Reactions with 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one

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Manuscript received 16 September 1976; Accepted 29 October 1976.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one has been condensed with ferrocene aldehyde and 2-methyl heterocyclic quaternary salts giving (IIIa) and (IX a-c) respectively. The reaction of ferrocenyldine derivatives (III a,b) with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine, amines and urea has been investigated. Interaction of (IX a-c) with ferrocenealdehyde gives new types of asymmetrical monomethine cyanine dyes (X a-c).

It is well known that the 4-position of 2-pyrazolin-5-one is very reactive and undergoes the characteristic condensation reaction of the active methylene group¹⁻³. The condensation of (I a, b) with ferrocenealdehyde (II) yielded the corresponding 4-ferrocenyldine-1-phenyl (2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (III a, b).

I a, X=y=H; I b, X=y=NO₂,
Fc=C₅H₅-Fe-C₅H₄-(Ferrocenyl radical).

The alkylation of (I a) via Michael addition has also been done by its reaction with (III a). Thus, heating a mixture of (I a) with (III a) in presence of sodium ethoxide affected alkylation with formation of the Michael adducts 4, 4'-bis-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one ferrocenylmethane IV.

The compound (IV) can also be prepared by the reaction of one mole of (II) with two moles of (I). Investigation of the IR spectrum of compound (IV) revealed that this did not show absorption band at 1700 cm⁻¹ (due to carbonyl group) and show strong absorption band at about ~1618 cm⁻¹ (C=N) and at 3445 cm⁻¹ (OH broad) (intramolecular hydrogen bonding)*: This shows that compounds (IV) exist in the tautomeric enol form (IVb), which finds support by the recently reported studies on the IR spectra of 4-alkylpyrazolones⁵⁻⁸.

The addition property of the exocyclic C=C in position 4- in 4-ferrocenyldine-1-phenyl (2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (III a,b) conjugated with the carbonyl group prompted us to investigate their behaviour towards the action of hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine, piperidine and morpholine.

Hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine reacted with (IIIa, b) in boiling alcohol and gave 4-ferrocenyl-1-phenyl (2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-3-methyl, 1-3a, 4, 5-tetrahydropyrazolo (3, 4-c) pyrazole (Va, b) and 4-ferrocenyl-1-phenyl (2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-5-phenyl-3-

methyl-1, 3a, 4, 5-tetrahydropyrazolo (3,4-c) pyrazole (VI a, b).

The IR spectra of (VII a-d) shows absorptions at 1612 cm^{-1} and 1577 cm^{-1} (cyclic C=N) and OH

When the coloured benzene solution of (III a, b) was treated with piperidine or morpholine at room temperature, the colour changed. Concentration of the reaction mixture, then addition of light-petrol affected the separation of 4-(ferrocenyl, piperidyl or morpholy) methyl-1-phenyl (2, 4-dinitrophenyl) 3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (VII a-d).

(3450 cm^{-1} broad)⁴. This shows that they exist in the enolic form (VII B).

Urea reacted with (III a) to give product believed to be the oxazolinopyrazole derivative (VIII).

The mechanism of formation of (VIII) may be

- VII a, X=y=H ; R=NC₅H₁₀
- VII b, X=y=H ; R=NC₄H₉O
- VII c, X=y=NO₂ ; R=NC₅H₁₀
- VII d, X=y=NO₂ ; R=NC₄H₉O

probably formulated as in (Scheme 1), which finds support from the mechanism of the reaction of 4-arylidene-1, 3-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one with urea and methylurea¹⁰.

VIII
Scheme 1

The IR spectrum of (VIII) shows absorption at 1613 and 1590 cm^{-1} (Cyclic C=N) and 3060 cm^{-1} (NH group)⁴.

X a-c

It is of interest to note that asymmetrical 2'-monomethine cyanine dyes which were patented as powerful photosensitisers to blue-green light¹¹⁻¹³ and as good orthochromatic sensitizers¹⁴⁻¹⁷ were prepared through the reaction of 2-methyl heterocyclic quaternary salts with other heterocyclic quaternary salts preferably having halide atoms^{18, 19}.

Within this area, a new type of asymmetrical

IX

pyrazolinone monomethine cyanine dyes (IX a-c) were prepared through interaction of 1-phenyl (2,4-dinitrophenyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one with quaternary salts of α -picoline and quinaldine ethiodide in the presence of piperidine as a catalyst.

Interaction of (IX a-c) with ferrocenealdehyde gave the corresponding cyanine dyes of type (X a-c).

X

(X a-c) were also prepared by another alternative

route through interaction of (III a-c) with quaternary salts of α -picoline and quinaldine ethiodide.

The products (X a-c) from the two experiments have the same m.p.s, no depression in the mixed melting point determination and have the same IR spectra.

The pyrazolinone (I), which is a typical substance containing an active methylene group, can behave as an addenda or donor in Michael addition to the

XII a-e

carbon-carbon double bond in conjugated system O=C-C=C in an acceptor. The present work investigated the Micheal addition of (I) with ferrocenyl chalcones (XI a-e). It was found that, the addition of (I) to the chalcones (XI a-e) leads to the formation of the Michael adducts (XII a-e) resulting in alkylation of the pyrazolinone at C-4. The addition takes place in hot alcohol in the presence of sodium hydroxide. This result is in analogy with the previous alkylation reaction of pyrazolinone with mesityl oxide²⁰.

The IR spectrum of (XII a-e) shows well defined absorption bands in the range of 1700-1670 cm⁻¹ characteristic for (C=O group), 1600-1585 cm⁻¹ (C=N group) and 2905 cm⁻¹ for CH₂ group⁴.

Experimental

The infrared absorption spectra were determined with a Unicam SP. 1200 spectrophotometer using KBr Wafer technique. The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined with a Perkin-Elmer spectracord Model 4000 A. All melting points are not corrected.

Condensation of 1-phenyl (2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (I a, b) with ferrocenealdehyde. A mixture of (I a, b) (0.01 mole) and ferrocenealdehyde (II) (0.01 mole) in ethyl alcohol 50 ml was heated under reflux for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated and left to cool. The solid that separated was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to give deep violet crystals (yield 80%, 70% (III a and b).

IIIa—Found : C, 68.28 ; H, 4.90 ; N, 7.76 ; C₂₁H₁₈N₂O Fe. Required: C, 68.08 ; H, 4.89 ; N, 7.56. M.P. > 360°.

IIIb—Found : C, 55.23 ; H, 3.31 ; N, 12.30 ; C₂₁H₁₅N₄O₂Fe. Required: C, 55.11 ; H, 3.26 ; N, 12.20. M.P. 135°-6° (dec.).

Alkylation of (Ia) via Michael addition to (III a). Formation of (IV a or b).

Method (A) : To a boiling solution of (I) (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (50 ml.) was added a solution of sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.5 g sodium in 10 ml. absolute ethanol). The solution was cooled to room temperature and while stirring (IIIa) (0.01 mole) was added. Stirring was continued at 100° for 1 hr, during which the colour of the solution disappeared. The pale red alcoholic solution was concentrated to half its volume cooled, and acidified with 5% acetic acid. The solid product was crystallized from alcohol-acetic acid mixture.

Method (B) : A mixture of (Ia) (0.01 mole) and III a (0.02 mole) was heated in an oil bath at 160° for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was left to cool and the product formed was crystallized from alcohol-acetic acid mixture to give (IV) (Yield 73%). Found: C, 68.41 ; H, 5.23 ; N, 10.32 ; C₂₁H₂₈N₄O₂ Fe. Required: C, 68.37 ; H, 5.14 ; N, 10.29 ; M.P. 310°-11° (Dec.).

Action of hydrazine hydrate and/or phenylhydrazine on (III a and b). Formation of (V a,b) and (VI a,b). A solution of (III a and b) (0.005 mole) and hydrazine hydrate and/or phenyl hydrazine 10.006 mole) in ethanol (40 ml.) was heated under reflux for 10 hr. The solid separated after concentration and cooling was crystallized from benzene-alcohol mixture (1 : 1). The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Compound No.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis %	
			Found N	Required N
V a	295-6 (dec.)	50	14.41	14.58
V b	160-1 (dec.)	48	17.33	17.64
VI a	117-8 (dec.)	60	12.32	12.17
VI b	151-3 (dec.)	65	15.31	15.27

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

Reaction of (IIIa and b) with piperidine and/or morpholine formation of (VII a-d). A solution of (III a,b) (0.005 mole) and piperidine and/or morpholine (0.005 mole) in dry benzene (50 ml) was stirred for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The colour of the solution gradually faded to a pale red colour, after concentration light petrol, (40°-60°)(20ml) was added to the benzene solution, the precipitated solid was filtered and crystallized from alcohol-benzene mixture (2 : 1). The results are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compound No. (VII)	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis %	
			Found N	Required N
a	195-6 (dec.)	45	9.42	9.23
b	340 (dec.)	57	9.31	9.19
c	130-1 (dec.)	45	12.99	12.85
d	170-1 (dec.)	47	13.01	12.79

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

Action of urea on (III a). Formation of (VIII). A solution of (IIIa) (0.01 mole) and urea (0.01 mole) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The cold solution was poured to cold water, the solid product was crystallized from alcohol as red-violet crystals (yield 60%), M.P. 285°-6° (dec.).

Found: C, 65.83 ; H, 5.03 ; N, 11.21. C₂₁H₁₆N₄OFe. Required: C, 65.45 ; H, 4.96 ; N, 10.93.

Condensation of (Ia, b) with 2-methyl heterocyclic quaternary salts. Formation of (IX a-c). A solution of (I a,b) (0.01 mole) and α -picoline and/or quinaldine ethiodide (0.01 mole) in ethanol (40 ml.) and few drops of piperidine was refluxed for about 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 3 days at room temperature. After concentration and cooling, the cold solution was poured to cold acidified water, the solid product was crystallized from ethyl alcohol. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Compound No. (IX)	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max}	Analysis %	
					Found N	Required N
a	156-7	42	394	4500	10.51	10.37
b	199-200	67	375,478	1100, 1800	9.50	9.23
c	145-6	60	354,472	10100, 5725	13.00	12.84

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

Condensation of (IX a-c) with ferrocenyl aldehyde. Formation of (X a-c). A solution of (IX a-c) (0.02 mole) and ferrocenyl aldehyde (0.02 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 20 hr. After concentration and cooling the reaction mixture poured on cold acidic water. The solid product was recrystallized from alcohol. The results are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4

Compound No. (X)	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max}	Analysis %	
					Found N	Required N
a	200-1 (dec.)	45	500	2400	10.01	10.07
b	301-9 (dec.)	60	330,498	7500, 4020	6.67	6.44
c	220-1 (dec.)	70	365 498	159850, 92930	9.61	9.43

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

Reaction of ferrocenyl chalcones (XI a-c) with (Ia). Formation of (XII a-c). A hot solution of sodium hydroxide (1 g in 1 ml. H₂O) was added to a solution of (Ia) (0.01 mole) and chalcones (XI a-e) in ethyl alcohol at 40°. The mixture was kept over-

night and then poured into 250 ml H₂O. The solid product was filtered and crystallized from benzene-alcohol (1 : 1) mixture. The results are listed in Table 5.

TABLE 5

Compound No. (XII)	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis %	
				Found N	Required N
a	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	140-1	60	5.77	5.55
b	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ -	197-8	57	5.01	4.94
c	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	122-3	50	5.44	5.33
d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	152-3	70	5.51	5.38
e	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	102-3	67	5.13	4.92

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